

Entanglement Generation via Spatial Path Superposition

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Abstract—Entanglement generation and distribution is a core functionality of quantum networks. Traditional approaches to this functionality rely on chains of quantum repeaters or on manipulation of multipartite states. In this work, we explore an alternative paradigm that explores quantum coherence at propagation level, by enabling genuine quantum instantiations of communication channels, existing in superposed configurations. We demonstrate that this mechanism can be harnessed to generate both bipartite and multipartite entangled states from separable inputs. Specifically, we show that Bell states can be obtained from initially separable two-qubit states, through the superposition of two unitary quantum channels. The proposed approach is further extended to multipartite systems, by generating n -qubit GHZ and W states and thereby revealing the constructive role of superposed quantum operations in entanglement creation. Moreover, we analyze the robustness of the proposed scheme against noise, showing that the resulting states retain high fidelity and concurrence even under realistic imperfections. Our results suggest that, under appropriate quantum control, noisy superposed paths can be effectively harnessed to engineer entanglement generation and distribution in quantum networks.

Index Terms—Quantum Paths, Quantum Internet, Entanglement generation and distribution, ERC-CoG QNattyNet.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum entanglement constitutes the fundamental communication resource of the Quantum Internet [1], [2], enabling information transfer and coordination tasks that circumvent the constraints imposed by the no-cloning theorem. Thus, entanglement generation and distribution is a core functionality of quantum networks. Traditionally, this functionality relies on approaches such as chains of quantum repeaters or the manipulation of multipartite entangled states [3].

An alternative and still partially unexplored direction concerns the generation of entangled states, either bipartite or multipartite, by exploiting quantum coherence at propagation level. Specifically, quantum particles can traverse two or more paths in quantum superposition, thereby realizing genuine quantum instantiations of communication channels, that themselves exist in a superposed configuration. As demonstrated in [4], such superposition of paths can manifest in two distinct forms: the superposition of spatial trajectories [5], [6], [7] and

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Fig. 1: Photonic setup for the implementation of superposition of different paths. The two white square boxes represent polarizing beam splitter, \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} represent two quantum operations. The control qubit can be encoded in the polarization degrees of freedom. The input state can be represented using other degrees of freedom.

the superposition of the orders in which a particle traverses two or more channels [8], [9], usually referred to as quantum switch. A comparative overview of these two frameworks is presented in Table I. The quantum switch has been proven to offer remarkable capabilities, such as enabling communication with a non-zero channel capacity even when one of the two individual channels has zero capacity [10], [11], [12]. Moreover in [7], it was shown that the same input-output behavior of a quantum switch can be replicated through two sequential applications of spatially superposed paths, thereby revealing the connection between the two frameworks. Nevertheless, the experimental implementation of the quantum switch remains challenging [13], [14]. And, there is ongoing interpretative debate regarding whether current implementations represent a genuine quantum switch or merely a simulation of its behavior [15]. In contrast, the superposition of spatial paths is considerably easier to realize experimentally, as demonstrated by simple interferometric setups and potential implementations based on discrete quantum walks. Furthermore, its physical interpretation is well established [16]. Fig. 1 illustrates a Mach-Zehnder interferometric setup to implement a spatial superposition of quantum channels. In this configuration, two degrees of freedom of a quantum particle, such as polarization (or spin) and spatial mode, are employed: the polarization serves as a control qubit, while the spatial mode encodes an input quantum state.

Recent studies have also explored the generation of entan-

TABLE I: Comparison between quantum switch and path superposition approaches.

Approach	Physical Mechanism	Non-classical Features	Experimental Feasibility
Quantum switch	Superposition of causal orders	Superposition and non-commutativity	Challenging
Superposition of path (this work)	Spatial superposition	Superposition	Simple

glement within the aforementioned frameworks. In [17], the generation of multipartite entangled states via indefinite causal order was demonstrated, although the analysis was restricted to the causal indefiniteness of unitary gates. More recently, [18] proposed a protocol for the deterministic generation of multi-qubit entangled states across distant nodes, by relying on a preshared maximally entangled state and single-qubit operations within the same indefinite-causal framework. In [19], the superposition of the orders of single-qubit gates was instead analyzed as a viable approach to realize controlled operations, thereby enabling universal quantum computation.

However, to the best of our knowledge, the generation of entangled states through the superposition of spatial paths has not yet been investigated.

Motivated by this gap, this work demonstrates how the superposition of spatial quantum trajectories can be harnessed to engineer both bipartite and multipartite entangled states from separable initial states. The overarching vision is that, by exploiting quantum coherence at propagation level, entanglement could be generated and distributed simultaneously within a unified process. Exploring this perspective, however, is left as a direction for future research.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: in Section II the theoretical formalism of superposition of spatial paths is reviewed; in Section III the generation of Bell states from separable states using the superposition of two unitary quantum channels is presented; also in Section III the proposed approach is generalized to multipartite systems, by showing how n -qubit GHZ and W states can be obtained; in Section IV the robustness of the proposed procedure against noise is analyzed; in Section V conclusions are drawn.

II. SPATIAL SUPERPOSITION OF PATHS

An essential feature of quantum mechanics is the breakdown of the classical notion of a definite trajectory: unlike a classical particle constrained to a single path, a quantum particle can coherently traverse multiple paths simultaneously. The mathematical formalism underlying the superposition of spatial paths has been developed in [4]. This formalism is based on extending the Hilbert space associated to the considered quantum system by introducing the so-called vacuum state, which describes the situation where a given quantum channel is not traversed by any particle. This extension, combined with the inclusion of a quantum control system, realized as a qubit or, more generally, as a qudit, and depicted in Fig. 2, enables the description of a particle's propagation through one of the channels or through their quantum superposition.

Mathematically, the superposition of two unitary quantum operations, U_1 and U_2 , with the assistance of a controller ρ_c , is formalized as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}(U_1, U_2)(\rho_t) = \mathcal{S}(\rho_t \otimes \rho_c) \mathcal{S}^\dagger, \quad (1)$$

with $\mathcal{S} = U_1 \otimes |0_c\rangle\langle 0_c| + U_2 \otimes |1_c\rangle\langle 1_c|$. When the system instead evolves under a coherent superposition of quantum channels, the corresponding map is given by:

$$\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{E})(\rho_t) = \sum_{ij} S_{ij}(\rho_t \otimes \rho_c) S_{ij}^\dagger \quad (2)$$

with S_{ij} given by:

$$S_{ij} = K_i \beta_j \otimes |0_c\rangle\langle 0_c| + \alpha_i E_j \otimes |1_c\rangle\langle 1_c|. \quad (3)$$

Here, the channels \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} are characterized by the Kraus operators $\{K_i\}$ and $\{E_j\}$, and by the corresponding vacuum amplitudes $\{\alpha_i\}$ and $\{\beta_j\}$, respectively. The vacuum amplitudes should only satisfy the normalization condition $\sum_i \alpha_i^2 = 1$ and $\sum_j \beta_j^2 = 1$ [4]. The superposition of unitary gates in Eq. (1) is the special case of Eq. (2), where no environmental interaction occurs.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of superposition of two channels \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} . The control is initialized in the state $\rho_c = |+_c\rangle\langle +_c|$.

III. ENTANGLEMENT GENERATION VIA SPATIAL-PATH SUPERPOSITION

Here, we first investigate the generation of the Bell states and then we generalize the analysis to multipartite states, such as GHZ and W states.

The initial input state is a separable two-qubit state of the form $\rho_t = |00\rangle\langle 00|$. This separable state is subsequently subjected to a spatial superposition of quantum operations, governed by a control qubit, as formalized for Bell states by the following proposition.

Proposition 1. *A two-qubit separable state $\rho_t = |00\rangle\langle 00|$ evolving under a coherent superposition of bit-flip $X \otimes X$ and phase-flip $Z \otimes Z$ operations yields maximally entangled Bell*

state, regardless of the measurement outcome of the control qubit.

Proof. Please refer to Appendix A. \square

As proved in the appendix, our analysis reveals that the output state corresponding to the $|+c\rangle$ -basis measurement of control qubit is the Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$, whereas the one corresponding to the $|-c\rangle$ -basis measurement is the Bell state $|\Phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle - |11\rangle)$, which is LU-equivalent to $|\Phi^+\rangle$. Interestingly, for an arbitrary input separable state of the form $\rho_t = |\psi_t\rangle\langle\psi_t|$, with $|\psi_t\rangle = (a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle)^{\otimes 2}$, the resulting output states are still maximally entangled Bell states, independent of the relative amplitude of the input state.

The generation and distribution of maximally entangled two-qubit states (Bell pairs) is essential for quantum communication and networking. Beyond bipartite entanglement, multipartite states, where entanglement is shared among more than two parties, play also a crucial role. Among these, two classes – each enabling different network functionalities [20] – exhibit genuine multipartite entanglement, being non-factorizable across any partition of the Hilbert space: the GHZ and W states [21], [22], [23].

A. Generation of GHZ states

The generation of a GHZ state from a separable state through spatial superposition of paths is a straightforward extension of the technique previously introduced for the Bell-state generation. Indeed, it is easy to recognize that the Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle$ can be regarded as a 2-qubit instance of a GHZ state. In the general case of an n -qubits system, a n -qubit GHZ state can be generated by superposing the $X^{\otimes n}$ and $Z^{\otimes n}$ operations, as formalized in the following proposition.

Proposition 2. *An n -qubit separable state $\rho_t = |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n}$ evolving under a coherent superposition of bit-flip $X^{\otimes n}$ and phase-flip $Z^{\otimes n}$ operations deterministically yields a GHZ state of n -qubit.*

Proof. Please refer to Appendix A. \square

B. Generation of W states

The generation of W states, on the other hand, is considerably less intuitive and requires the superposition of more than two distinct operations. Specifically, to generate an n -qubit W state, the system must evolve through a coherent superposition of n unitaries. This, in turn, implies that the auxiliary system controlling these trajectories can no longer be a simple qubit, but must, instead, be a higher-dimensional system, an n -level system (qudit). The computational basis of this qudit is $B = \{|i\rangle, i = 0, \dots, n-1\}$. Consequently, the overall system evolves into a superposition of all paths when the control qudit is initially prepared in the state $|\psi\rangle = 1/\sqrt{n} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} |i\rangle$. Within this framework, it becomes necessary to define explicitly the set of operators to be superposed in order to produce the desired evolution. We denote these operators as $X_i \triangleq \mathbb{I}_0 \otimes \mathbb{I}_2 \dots \otimes \mathbb{I}_{i-1} \otimes X \otimes \mathbb{I}_{i+1} \otimes \dots \otimes \mathbb{I}_{n-1}$, which represent the tensor product of n operators that are all

Fig. 3: Schematic diagram illustrating the superposition of three paths used to generate a 3-qubit W state. The control qubit is in the state $|e_+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle + |2\rangle)$ and the input target state is $\rho_t = |000\rangle\langle 000|$. The unitary operations are $X_0 \triangleq X \otimes I \otimes I$, $X_1 \triangleq I \otimes X \otimes I$ and $X_2 \triangleq I \otimes I \otimes X$.

identities except for the i -th one, which is an X gate. The setup for a 3-qubit W state is shown in Fig. 3.

Proposition 3. *An n -qubit separable state $\rho_t = |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n}$ evolving under a coherent superposition of the n operators X_i deterministically yields the n -qubit W state.*

Proof. Please refer to Appendix B. \square

IV. ROBUSTNESS AGAINST NOISE

In this section, we relax the assumption made in Section III, namely that entanglement generation exploits the superposition of unitary operations. Instead, we investigate how imperfections and noise in quantum operations affect the entanglement generation process. We first briefly introduce the bit-flip and phase-flip channels, used to model noisy quantum paths.

1) *Bit-flip channel:* The bit-flip channel introduces an error by flipping the computational basis states of a qubit, *i.e.*, $|0\rangle \leftrightarrow |1\rangle$. The correlated action of this channel on two qubit can be represented by the following Kraus operators:

$$K_0 = \sqrt{1-p} I \otimes I, \quad K_1 = \sqrt{p} X \otimes X, \quad (4)$$

with X denoting the Pauli- X matrix and p the probability of a bit-flip error.

2) *Phase-flip channel:* The phase-flip channel introduces a phase error by inverting the relative phase between the computational basis states, *i.e.*, $|0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle \rightarrow -|1\rangle$. The Kraus operators describing two qubit correlated phase-flip channel are given by:

$$E_0 = \sqrt{1-q} I \otimes I, \quad E_1 = \sqrt{q} Z \otimes Z, \quad (5)$$

where Z denotes the Pauli- Z matrix and q represents the phase-flip error probability.

It is possible to demonstrate that the generation of entangled states through spatial-path superposition exhibits a notable resistance to noise. To substantiate this robustness, we analyze the case of Bell-state generation under noisy conditions, modeled by the previously defined quantum maps, \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} :

$$\mathcal{K}(\rho_t) = (1-p)\rho_t + p(X \otimes X)\rho_t(X \otimes X); \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{E}(\rho_t) = (1-q)\rho_t + q(Z \otimes Z)\rho_t(Z \otimes Z). \quad (7)$$

Within our framework, Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) can be interpreted as: with probability p (or q), the operation $X \otimes X(Z \otimes Z)$ is applied, while with probability $1 - p$ the gate application fails due to environmental interactions. By combining these definitions with Eq. (3), the map \mathcal{S} describing the joint evolution of the system and the control qubits is characterized by the Kraus operators:

$$S_{ij} = \beta_j K_i \otimes |0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| + \alpha_i E_j \otimes |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c|, \quad (8)$$

where $\{K_i\}(\{E_j\})$ are the two qubit correlated Kraus operators associated to the map $\mathcal{K}(\mathcal{E})$ given in Eqs. 4 and 5, and $\{\alpha_i\}(\{\beta_j\})$ are the corresponding vacuum amplitudes. As shown in Appendix C, substituting Eq. (8) in Eq. (2) and measuring the control qubit yield the output state:

$$\rho_{out}^{\pm} = \sum_{ij} (\beta_j K_i \pm \alpha_i E_j) \rho_t (\beta_j^* K_i^{\dagger} \pm \alpha_i^* E_j^{\dagger}). \quad (9)$$

In the following, we assess the properties of the state in Eq. (9), generated by exploiting the proposed framework, in terms of entanglement features, by focusing on the measured control state $|+_c\rangle$, since analogous considerations hold for $|-_c\rangle$. Accordingly, Eq. (9) can be specialized as:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{out}^+ = & C [((2 + (\alpha_0 \beta_0^* + \alpha_0^* \beta_0) \sqrt{(1-p)(1-q)}) \\ & + (\alpha_0 \beta_1^* + \alpha_0^* \beta_1) \sqrt{(1-p)q - p}) |00\rangle \langle 00| \\ & + (\alpha_1 \beta_0^* \sqrt{(1-q)p} + \alpha_1 \beta_1^* \sqrt{qp}) |00\rangle \langle 11| \\ & + (\alpha_1^* \beta_0 \sqrt{(1-q)p} + \alpha_1^* \beta_1 \sqrt{qp}) |11\rangle \langle 00| + p |11\rangle \langle 11|], \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

with $C = 1 / (2 + (\alpha_0 \beta_0^* + \alpha_0^* \beta_0) \sqrt{(1-p)(1-q)} + (\alpha_0 \beta_1^* + \alpha_0^* \beta_1) \sqrt{(1-p)q})$. To assess the robustness of the proposed framework against noise, we evaluate the fidelity of the generated state, defined as $F(\rho_{out}^+, \rho_{|\Phi^+\rangle}) = \text{Tr} \left[\sqrt{\sqrt{\rho_{out}^+} \rho_{|\Phi^+\rangle} \sqrt{\rho_{out}^+}} \right]$, with $\rho_{|\Phi^+\rangle}$ indicating the density matrix of the Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle$. Additionally, we quantify the degree of entanglement through the concurrence, which represents a rigorous entanglement measure for 2-qubit systems, valid even for mixed states [24], [25]. The analysis is performed for different values of the vacuum amplitudes, to explore their impact on fidelity and entanglement robustness. Our choice of vacuum amplitude is not restrictive, as it can be freely selected, provided normalization conditions are met, while a full optimization analysis is left for future work.

As shown in Figures 4 and 5, increasing the probability of successful-gate application drives the generated state progressively closer to the Bell state $|\Phi^+\rangle$, but it never reaches perfect fidelity for some choices of vacuum amplitudes. This behavior is also evident from the concurrence in Fig. 4, which remains below unity. In contrast, for other values of the vacuum amplitudes, both fidelity and concurrence exhibit a linear growth with the success probability and eventually reach unity. It is important to notice that for all the considered cases, the fidelity remains above the threshold value required for entanglement distillation [26], indicating that even in presence of noise, the proposed framework can generate entangled

states useful for quantum communication protocols.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have shown that the superposition of spatial paths provides a powerful and experimentally feasible framework for generating entanglement in quantum network, both in the bipartite and multipartite regimes. The proposal proved that, starting from a separable state, the superposition of quantum paths enables the deterministic generation of Bell states as well as genuinely multipartite GHZ and W states. Furthermore, we evaluated the robustness of the framework against noise, by relaxing the ideal assumption of unitary quantum channels. The analysis revealed that the resulting states retain high fidelity and concurrence even under realistic imperfections. Although these results represent a first step, they demonstrate that, under appropriate quantum control, noisy superposed paths can be effectively harnessed to engineer entanglement generation in quantum networks. Interestingly, it is the noise on the channels themselves that can be exploited as a resource for entanglement generation. The overarching vision is that, by exploiting quantum coherence at propagation level, entanglement could be generated and distributed simultaneously within a unified process. Exploring this perspective remains an exciting direction for future research.

APPENDIX

A. Generation of Bell and GHZ states

For Bell states, we consider the state $|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$. This choice does not entail any loss of generality, since all Bell states are equivalent under local unitaries (LU). Taking as input state $\rho = \rho_t \otimes \rho_c = |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} \otimes |+_c\rangle \langle +_c|$ and applying the operator $S = X^{\otimes n} |0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| + Z^{\otimes n} |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c|$, Eq. (1) is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} S \rho S^{\dagger} = & (X^{\otimes n} |0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| + Z^{\otimes n} |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c|) (|0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} \otimes |+_c\rangle \langle +_c|) \\ & ((X^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| + (Z^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c|) \\ = & \frac{1}{2} (X^{\otimes n} |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} (X^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \\ & + X^{\otimes n} |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} (Z^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |0_c\rangle \langle 1_c| \\ & + Z^{\otimes n} |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} (X^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |1_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \\ & + Z^{\otimes n} |0\rangle^{\otimes n} \langle 0|^{\otimes n} (Z^{\otimes n})^{\dagger} |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c|). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

By expressing the control qubit in $|\pm_c\rangle$ basis and measuring the control qubit in the state $|+_c\rangle \langle -_c|$, the system ends up in the state $|GHZ^{\pm}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle^{\otimes n} \pm |1\rangle^{\otimes n})$. As evident from the above expression, when $n = 2$, the resultant state corresponds to the 2-qubit Bell state $|\Phi^{\pm}\rangle$.

B. Generation of W states

For clarity and due to page limitations, we provide the proof for the three-qubit W state case.

By taking as input state $\rho = \rho_t \otimes \rho_c = |000\rangle \langle 000| \otimes |e_+\rangle \langle e_+|$, with $|e_+\rangle = (1/\sqrt{3})(|0\rangle + |1\rangle + |2\rangle)$ and applying the operator

Fig. 4: (a) Fidelity versus gate-application success probability ($p = q$), for three vacuum amplitude configurations. The solid blue curve, corresponding to equal vacuum amplitudes $\alpha_i = \beta_i = 1/\sqrt{2}$, shows increasing fidelity with p , though it never reaches unity. The dotted orange curve for $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 1/\sqrt{3}$ and $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 = \sqrt{2/3}$ exhibits a steeper rise and achieves higher fidelity than the blue case. In contrast, the dashed green curve, for $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 0$ and $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 = 1$, exhibits a linear increase, reaching perfect fidelity at $p = 1$. In all the considered scenarios, the fidelity remains above the purification threshold even for $p = 0$. (b) Concurrence versus success probability $p = q$, for the same set of vacuum amplitudes. The solid blue curve ($\alpha_i = \beta_i = 1/\sqrt{2}$) shows that entanglement increases with p but never reaches unity. The dotted orange curve ($\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 1/\sqrt{3}, \alpha_1 = \beta_1 = \sqrt{2/3}$) rises above the blue one but still falls short of unity. Finally, the dashed green curve ($\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 0, \alpha_1 = \beta_1 = 1$) exhibits a linear growth, reaching maximal concurrence when the gate-application probability p equals one.

Fig. 5: Density plot showing Fidelity against success-gate probability p and q of succeeding in application of the $X \otimes X$ and $Z \otimes Z$ gates respectively for three different vacuum amplitudes configurations: (a) $\alpha_i = \beta_i = 1/\sqrt{2}$, even for $p = q = 0$ the fidelity value is above the purification threshold. (b) $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 1/\sqrt{3}$ and $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 = \sqrt{2/3}$, the fidelity in this case is higher than in (a), but it doesn't reach 1. (c) $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 0$ and $\alpha_1 = \beta_1 = 1$, also in this case, even for $p = q = 0$ the Fidelity value is above the purification threshold, and in this case Fidelity reaches 1 for $p = q = 1$.

$S = X_0 |0\rangle\langle 0| + X_1 |1\rangle\langle 1| + X_2 |2\rangle\langle 2|$, where X_i are the operators defined in Section III-B, Eq. (1) is given by:

$$S\rho S^\dagger = \sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} X_l |l\rangle\langle l| \rho X_m^\dagger |m\rangle\langle m| \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ X_1 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_0^\dagger |1\rangle\langle 0| \\ &+ X_1 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_1^\dagger |1\rangle\langle 1| + \\ &+ X_1 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_2^\dagger |1\rangle\langle 2| \\ &+ X_2 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_0^\dagger |2\rangle\langle 0| + \\ &+ X_2 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_1^\dagger |2\rangle\langle 1| \\ &+ X_2 |000\rangle\langle 000| X_2^\dagger |2\rangle\langle 2|. \end{aligned}$$

By expressing the computational basis of the control qutrit in the orthonormal basis $\{|e_+\rangle, |e_-\rangle, |e_*\rangle\}$, where $|e_-\rangle = 1/\sqrt{3}(|0\rangle + \omega|1\rangle + \omega^2|2\rangle)$, $|e_*\rangle = 1/\sqrt{3}(|0\rangle + \omega^2|1\rangle + \omega|2\rangle)$, with $\omega = \exp(2\pi i/3)$, and measuring the control qutrit in the $|e_+\rangle$, the system ends up in the W state

$$|W\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}(|100\rangle + |010\rangle + |001\rangle). \quad (13)$$

If we measure the control qubit in one of the other states of the basis, the generated state is equivalent to a W state up to local operations. Thus, the generation of the W state is deterministic.

C. Generation of Bell state through noisy-path superposition

The joint unitary evolution of system, control and environment can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \left[|0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \otimes \sum_{ii'} K_i \rho_t K_{i'}^\dagger \otimes |i\rangle \langle i'|^\mathcal{K} \otimes |\epsilon_1\rangle \langle \epsilon_1|^\mathcal{E} \right. \\ & + |0_c\rangle \langle 1_c| \otimes \sum_{ij'} K_i \rho_t E_{j'}^\dagger \otimes |i\rangle \langle \epsilon_0|^\mathcal{K} \otimes |\epsilon_1\rangle \langle j'|^\mathcal{E} \\ & + |1_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \otimes \sum_{ij} E_j \rho_t K_i^\dagger \otimes |\epsilon_0\rangle \langle i'|^\mathcal{K} \otimes |j\rangle \langle \epsilon_1|^\mathcal{E} \\ & \left. + |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c| \otimes \sum_{jj'} E_j \rho_t E_{j'}^\dagger \otimes |\epsilon_0\rangle \langle \epsilon_0|^\mathcal{K} \otimes |j\rangle \langle j'|^\mathcal{E} \right] \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

where, $|\epsilon_0\rangle = \sum_i \alpha_i |i\rangle$ and $|\epsilon_1\rangle = \sum_j \beta_j |j\rangle$ are the environmental state with $|i\rangle$ and $|j\rangle$ are orthonormal basis, corresponding to channels \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{E} respectively. Taking the partial trace over the environment, we obtain the system evolution as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{K}, \mathcal{E})(\rho_t) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[|0_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \otimes \sum_{ij} K_i \rho_t K_i^\dagger \langle j|\epsilon_1\rangle \langle \epsilon_1|j\rangle \right. \\ & + |0_c\rangle \langle 1_c| \otimes \sum_{ij} K_i \rho_t E_j^\dagger \langle \epsilon_0|i\rangle \langle j|\epsilon_1\rangle \\ & + |1_c\rangle \langle 0_c| \otimes \sum_{ij} E_j \rho_t K_i^\dagger \langle i|\epsilon_0\rangle \langle \epsilon_1|j\rangle \\ & \left. + |1_c\rangle \langle 1_c| \otimes \sum_{ij} E_j \rho_t E_j^\dagger \otimes \langle i|\epsilon_0\rangle \langle \epsilon_0|i\rangle \right]. \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

In the above equation $\beta_j = \langle \epsilon_1|j\rangle$ and $\alpha_i = \langle \epsilon_0|i\rangle$ represent the vacuum amplitudes, which satisfy $\sum_i |\alpha_i|^2 = 1$ and $\sum_j |\beta_j|^2 = 1$. When the control qubit is measured in the $|+c\rangle$ ($-c$), the output state has the following form

$$\rho_{out}^\pm = \sum_{ij} (\beta_j K_i \pm \alpha_i E_j) \rho_t (\beta_j^* K_i^\dagger \pm \alpha_i^* E_j^\dagger). \quad (16)$$

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